

Interacting blends of acrylated poly(ester-amide)s containing epoxy residues with vinyl ester resin

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Abstract : Unsaturated bisamic acids were prepared by reaction between maleic anhydride and different aliphatic diamines. Unsaturated poly(ester-amide) resin (UPEAs) were prepared by reaction of diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DGEBA) with unsaturated bisamic acids derived from. Acrylation of UPEAs was carried out to afford acrylated UPEAs resin (i.e. AUPEAs). Interacting blends of AUPEAs with vinyl ester epoxy (VE) resin was prepared. APEAs and AUPEAs were characterized by elemental analysis, molecular weight determined by vapour pressure osmometer and by IR spectral study and by thermogravimetry. The curing of interacting blends were monitored on differential scanning calorimeter (DSC). Based on DSC data *in situ* glass reinforced composites of the resultant blends have been prepared and characterized for mechanical, electrical and chemical properties. Unreinforced blends were characterized by thermogravimetrically (TGA).

Keywords : Unsaturated bisamic acid, unsaturated poly(ester-amide) resin (UPEAs), acrylated unsaturated poly(ester-amide) resin (AUPEAs), composites, vinyl ester epoxy (VE) resin.

Introduction

The epoxy resins are used in large number of fields, including surface coatings, in adhesives, reinforced with carbon fiber^{1,2}. The polyesters are most widely versatile materials and have broad spectrum of characteristics and wide applications ranging from aerospace to micro electronics. They are also important as laminating resins, moulding composites, fibers, films, surface coating resins and fiber cushion^{3,4}. Polyamides material used in the form of fibers especially thermoplastics have been used in certain engineering applications. The glass fiber reinforced nylon plastics are of substantial importance due to rigidity and creep resistance. Polyamides have also been used in fiber application, automotive industries, valve covers and anticorrosive coatings^{5,6}.

Merging of all the four unsaturation, epoxy, ester and amide segments into one polymer chain has not received attention academically and technically. Merging of all three segments (i.e. epoxy, ester and amide) into saturated and unsaturated polymer chain has been recently

reported from our Indian scientists⁷⁻¹⁰. Certain properties of thermoplastics may also be improved via blending or addition to a thermoset is another possibility. In order to improve certain properties blending with commercial vinyl esters (epoxy resin) such vinyl ester epoxy resin is a commercial important material for wide industrial applications^{11,12}. Hence the present paper comprises interacting blending of reported unsaturated poly(ester-amide) resin with vinyl ester (VE) resin. Also, glass fiber reinforced composites of these blends have been laminated and characterized by chemical, mechanical and electrical properties. The whole work is scanned in Scheme 1.

Experimental

Materials :

Commercially available epoxy resin, diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A and vinyl ester epoxy resins were obtained from local market. The specification of diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DGEBA) are epoxy equivalent weight 190, viscosity 40-100 poise at 25 °C, density at

Scheme 1. Synthesis steps.

25 °C 1.16–1.17 g m⁻¹ vinyl ester epoxy.

The diamines used for the preparation of unsaturated poly(ester-amide) resin are, 1,2-ethylene diamine, 1,2-propylene diamine and 1,6-hexamethylene diamine.

Plain weave fibers, in the form of E-glass woven fabric (poly(ester-amide) compatible) 0.25 mm thick (Unnati Chemicals, India) of a real weight 270 g m⁻² were used for composite fabrication. All other chemicals used were of pure grade.

Methods :

Synthesis of unsaturated bisamic acids :

The unsaturated bisamic acid was prepared by a simple addition reaction of maleic anhydride and diamines. These were prepared by using method reported in the literature^{7,8}. The general procedure for the synthesis of unsaturated bisamic acid is as follows :

To a well-stirred solution of maleic anhydride (2.0 mol) in dry acetone, the solution of diamine (1.0 mol) in dry acetone was gradually added at 0–5 °C within 30 min. After complete addition of the diamine, the reaction mixture was further stirred for half an hour at room temperature. The resulting unsaturated bisamic acid was then filtered, washed with dry acetone and air-dried. Unsaturated bisamic acid was obtained in the form of free flowing powder. The reaction scheme for the synthesis of unsaturated bisamic acid is shown in Scheme 1.

Synthesis of unsaturated poly(ester-amide) resin and acrylated poly(ester-amide) resin :

The unsaturated poly(ester-amide) resin (UPEAs) was

prepared by following the same method reported in Refs 7, 8. The general procedure is as follows :

Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DGEBA) (1.0 mol) and unsaturated bisamic acid (1.0 mol) were charged in three necked flask equipped with a mechanical stirrer. The unsaturated bisamic acid was then treated with diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A according to method reported for reaction of epoxy resin and carboxylic group¹³. To this 8.0% of the total weight of above, triethylamine (TEA) was added as a base catalyst. The reaction mixture was slowly heated up to 85 °C with continuous stirring till the acid value fell below 60 mg KOH gm⁻¹. The resultant resin was then discharged and called unsaturated poly(ester-amide) resin (UPEAs) and their details are furnished in Table 1. Further reaction of all these unsaturated poly(ester-amide) resin (UPEAs) was carried out with acryloyl chloride (i.e. acrylation) and the resultant products called acrylated poly(ester-amide)s (APEAs) and their details are furnished in Table 2.

Synthesis of acrylated poly(ester-amide) resin and vinyl ester resin blend :

When the acid value of acrylated poly(ester-amide)s fell below 55 mg KOH gm⁻¹, 0.05% of hydroquinone was added as an inhibitor. The whole reaction stirred well for 10 min maintaining the temperature at 85 °C. Then add 50% of APEAs and 50% of vinyl ester (VE) resin was added and stirred well at 80 °C for 1 h. The resultant APEAs-VE blends were obtained in the form of viscous syrup.

Table 1. Characterization of UPEAs (2a-c)

UPEAs	Elemental analysis (Wt%) :			No. of -OH group per repeating unit	Number average molecular weight (\overline{M}_n) ± 60
	Calcd./(Found) (%)				
	C	H	N		
3a	59.23 (58.86)	5.73 (5.11)	4.45 (3.75)	1.91	3734
3b	59.81 (59.05)	4.36 (3.86)	4.36 (3.78)	1.89	3816
3c	61.40 (60.71)	4.09 (3.26)	4.09 (3.67)	1.94	4160

Table 2. Characterization of AUPEAs (4a-c)

AUPEAs	Elemental analysis (Wt%) :			No. of double bonds per repeating unit	Number average molecular weight (\overline{M}_n) ± 60
	Calcd./(Found) (%)				
	C	H	N		
4a	65.29 (64.79)	5.88 (5.09)	4.11 (3.79)	3.91	4045
4b	65.70 (64.92)	6.05 (5.42)	4.03 (3.58)	3.95	4121
4c	66.84 (66.11)	6.52 (6.85)	3.80 (3.41)	3.93	4382

Analysis and thermal studies :

Elemental analysis :

The C, H, N content of unsaturated poly(ester-amide)s (UPEAs) and acrylated poly(ester-amide)s (APEAs) was estimated by means of Thermofinagan 1101 flash elemental analyzer (Italy). The IR spectra were recorded in Kerr pellets on a Nicollet 760 D spectrometer. The number average weight of unsaturated poly(ester-amide)s (UPEAs) and acrylated poly(ester-amide)s (APEAs) was estimated by non-aqueous conductometric titration following by method reported in the literature¹⁴. Pyridine was used as a solvent and tetra-*n*-butyl ammonium hydroxide was used as a titrant.

Thermal study :

Curing of all APEAs-VE blends were carried out on a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) by using benzoyl peroxide as a catalyst. A Du Pont 900 DSC was used for this study. The instrument was calibrated using standard indium metal with known heat of fusion ($\Delta H = 28.45 \text{ Jg}^{-1}$). Curing was carried out from 30–300 °C at 10 °C min⁻¹ heating rate. The sample weight used for this investigation was in the range of 4–5 mg along with an empty reference cell. The results are furnished in Table 3.

Table 3. DSC curing of UAPEAs-vinyl ester epoxy resin blends (5a-c)

UAPEAs-VE resin blends	Curing temp. (°C)		
	T_i	T_p	T_f
5a	114	137	156
5b	109	132	154
5c	107	129	150

Unreinforced cured samples of APEAs-VE blends were subjected to thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) on Du Pont 950 thermogravimetric analyzer in air at a heating

rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. The sample weight used for this investigation was in the range of 4–5 mg. The results are furnished in Table 4.

Table 4. TGA of unreinforced cured samples of UAPEAs-vinyl ester epoxy resin blends (5a-c)-BPO system

UAPEAs-VE resin blends	% Weight loss at various temp. (°C) from TGA				
	150	300	450	600	750
5a	2.75	10.21	70.61	79.33	82.97
5b	2.59	10.09	70.14	79.30	82.23
5c	2.28	9.83	69.93	78.80	82.11

Composite fabrication :

The composites were prepared by using E-type of glass fiber. The glass fiber : APEAs-VE blend ratio is 60 : 40 (40% APEAs-VE blends). Suspensions of APEAs-VE blends were prepared in tetrahydrofuran (THF). In the above polymer suspension, 1% of ethylene dimethylacrylate (as a cross linking agent) with 0.05% benzoyl peroxide (as an initiator) were added and mixed well. The mixture was applied with a brush to a 200 mm × 200 mm glass cloth and the solvent was allowed to evaporate. The ten dried prepregs prepared in this way were then stacked one on top of another and pressed between steel plates coated with a “Teflon” film release sheet and compressed under 70 psi pressure. The prepregs stacks were cured by heating it in an autoclave oven at around 140 °C for about 6 h. The composites so obtained were cooled to 45–50 °C before the pressure was released.

Composite characterizations :

Chemical resistance test :

The resistances against chemicals of the composites were measured according to ASTM D 543. The results are furnished in Table 5.

Table 5. Chemical, mechanical and electrical properties of composites based on APEAs-MMA blends

Composites	% Change on exposure to 25% (w/v) NaOH		Compressive strength (MPa)	Impact strength (MPa)	Rockwell hardness (R)	Electrical strength (in air) (kV mm ⁻¹)
	Thickness	Weight				
5b	0.89	1.20	403	411	101	20.5
5c	0.84	1.18	408	408	98	20.9

Mechanical and electrical testing :

(i) The flexural strength was measured according to ASTM D 790.

(ii) The compressive strength was measured according to ASTM D 695.

(iii) The impact strength was measured according to ASTM D 256.

(iv) The rockwell hardness was measured according to ASTM D 785.

(v) The electrical strength was measured according to ASTM D 149.

All mechanical and electrical tests were performed using three specimens and their average results are summarized in Table 5.

Results and discussion

The unsaturated bisamic acids were prepared by the reaction of maleic anhydride (2.0 mol) and aliphatic diamines (1.0 mol) by following method reported in literature^{7,8}. Unsaturated poly(ester-amide)s (PEAs) was prepared by reaction of epoxy resin (DGEBA) with unsaturated bisamic acids using triethylamine (TEA) as a base catalyst. The post reactions of all these unsaturated poly(ester-amide)s (PEAs) were carried out with acryloyl chloride. The resultant products are called acrylated poly(ester-amide)s (APEAs). Blending of acrylated poly(ester-amide)s (APEAs) with vinyl ester (VE) resin was also carried out. The resultant products are called APEAs-VE blends.

The C, H, N contents of all the unsaturated poly(ester-amide)s (PEAs) and acrylated poly(ester-amide)s (APEAs) were estimated by means of Thermofinagan 1101 Flash Elemental Analyzer (Italy). The values of C, H, N of each of the unsaturated poly(ester-amide)s (PEAs) and acrylated poly(ester-amide)s (APEAs) were consistent with their predicted structures and are furnished in Tables 1 and 2. The average molecular weight of both unsaturated poly(ester-amide)s (PEAs) and acrylated poly(ester-amide)s (APEAs) were estimated by non-aqueous conductometric titration method¹⁴. Their results are furnished in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. The results indicate that the degree of polymerization of both unsaturated poly(ester-amide)s (PEAs) and acrylated poly(ester-amide)s (APEAs) is about 6. The IR spectra were consistent with the ones expected

from the structures of the PEAs (3a-c) and APEAs (4a-c).

Numbers of hydroxyl group present per repeating unit in unsaturated poly(ester-amide)s (PEAs) was also analyzed by employing acetylating method¹⁵. Also, acrylated poly(ester-amide)s (APEAs) were characterized for the presence of double bonds per repeating unit employing mercury-catalyzed bromate-bromide method¹⁶. Satisfactory results were found and the results are furnished in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

Curing of all these APEAs-VE blends were carried out on a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) by using benzoyl peroxide as a catalyst. The data of DSC thermograms of all APEAs-VE are furnished in Table 3.

The unreinforced cured samples of APEAs-VE blends were also analyzed by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). The result reveals that the cured sample starts their degradation at about 150 °C and their initial weight is about 2-3%. This small weight loss may be due to either in sufficient curing of components used or due to the catalyst used. A weight loss of about 10-11% is found at 300 °C. However, the rate of decomposition increases very rapidly between 300 °C to 450 °C and the products are lost completely beyond 750 °C. TGA data of all the samples are shown in Table 4.

The glass and carbon fiber reinforced composites of all APEAs-VE blends were prepared based on their DSC data. The composites were characterized for their chemical, mechanical and electrical properties. Their results are furnished in Table 5. The results shows that composites have good chemical resistant property, good mechanical and electrical strength.

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